

Collaboration, knowledge exchange and joint initiatives

Deliverable 10.3

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DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

Dissemination level

PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page))	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Table of contents

Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction.....	6
1.1 Background.....	6
1.2 Overview of specified Horizon Europe Clusters	6
1.2.1 HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-20	6
1.2.2 HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1.....	6
1.2.3 HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-3.....	7
2. Methodology for identifying potential collaborators.....	7
3. Scan of existing projects and networks	8
4. Establishing synergies and strategic links (Connect)	9
4.1 OrganicAdviceNetwork (Grant ID 101134850) (HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-20)	9
4.2 Organic Yields UP (Grant ID 101137068) (HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-3)	10
4.3 SCALE-it (Grant ID 101181496) - HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1 (two-stage).....	11
4.4 BIO2 (Grant ID 101181331)- HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1 (two-stage)	12
5. Follow-up approach (Connect / Organize).....	13
5.1 Regular update of the OH-FINE coordination tracker	13
5.2 Follow-up communication and collaboration survey	14

List of Tables

Table 1. General Summary of the five phases of the SCOPE methodology	7
Table 2. Links established between OH-FINE and shortlisted HE projects	13
Annex	
Table 1. Long List of Thematically Aligned EU Research Projects.....	15
Table 2. OHFINE EU project Communication and Collaboration Record ..	19

List of Figures

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Executive Summary

Organic Farming Innovations Network Europe OH-FINE has a duration of 48 months, starting from the 1st of November 2024, and is funded by the European Union in the framework of Horizon Europe, the European Union's Research and Innovation Programme 2021-2027, and by SERI, the Swiss Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation. The project is coordinated by the Institute of Natural Resources and Agrobiology of Salamanca (IRNASA), which is part of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). The project focusses in empowering European farmers by advancing and sharing sustainable organic farming knowledge and solutions that align with farmer capabilities, consumer demands, and evolving food market trends. The project involves 18 partners from 9 countries.

Work Package 10 focuses on making relevant stakeholders aware of the OH-FINE project, broadly promoting the project through diverse channels, providing easy access to information and results on its website, widely disseminating project findings through customized materials in partner countries, and securing the project's legacy and long-term accessibility of its outcomes.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

As required under Horizon Europe, OH-FINE includes a dedicated task, allocated resources, and an operational plan to ensure structured collaboration with other projects funded under the same call topic (HORIZON-CL6-2022-GOVERNANCE-01-10), and to maximise synergies with projects funded under related thematic call areas within Cluster 6, including (specifically HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-20, HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1, and HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-3) throughout the duration of the project. This begins with an information gathering process on relevant project objectives, methodologies and key contact persons to pinpoint areas of synergy and mutual benefit. This information will be used to identify where collaboration can be most beneficial, the activities to be undertaken to maximise synergies (which may include joint workshops, cross-field visits, meetings of farmers and other stakeholders, involvement in training activities, joint networking, collective policy recommendations, etc.) and the resources needed to carry out such collaboration.

1.2 Overview of specified Horizon Europe Clusters

1.2.1 HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-20

This call focuses on the important role that advisors can play in relation to boosting organic farming towards reaching the target of at least 25% of the EU's agricultural land under organic farming by 2030. This cluster is focused on Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) and the role of advisors within the AKIS to facilitate innovation and the uptake of research results by farmers.

1.2.2 HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1

Projects under this call support the objective of the farm to fork strategy to transition to fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food systems from primary production to consumption, notably the objective to promote and increase organic farming in Europe, in line with the target of at least 25% of the EU's agricultural land under organic farming by 2030. Activities support the implementation of concrete actions in the EU action plan for the development of organic production and of Regulation (EU) 2018/848 on the rules on organic production and labelling of organic products. Activities will also support the farm to fork and biodiversity strategies' objective to reduce the risk and use of chemical pesticides by 50% and the use of more hazardous pesticides by 50%. Overall, projects under this call aim to phase out and replace contentious inputs used in organic farming, and to increase the availability, accessibility and use of alternatives to these products through multi-stakeholder approaches.

1.2.3 HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-3

This call focuses on one of the key obstacles that hinders conversion to organic farming - the fact that several crops grown under organic conditions achieve lower yields per hectare as compared with those produced under conventional farming practices. Projects focus on closing the yield gap in order to further improve the economic competitiveness and resilience of the sector, as well as to increase farmers' adoption of organic production. Using participatory approaches, projects aim to set up a European-wide network of testing, experimentation and demonstration sites to test, co-create and showcase practices and strategies that improve yields of crops produced under organic conditions.

2. Methodology for identifying potential collaborators

The OH-FINE project developed the 'Scan, Connect, Organise, Prevent and Evaluate' (SCOPE) methodology under WP2 to screen ongoing Horizon Europe funded projects and act as a coordination mechanism to foster possible collaborations. The SCOPE methodology is applied across the OH-FINE project to ensure that duplication is prevented, and synergies are identified and leveraged. Table 1 outlines the phases of the SCOPE methodology as presented in Deliverable 2.7 under WP2. This deliverable builds on the SCOPE methodology and outlines the structured and proactive approach to collaboration taken thus far in the project.

Table 1. General Summary of the five phases of the SCOPE methodology

Phase	Objective
Scan	Identify existing projects and networks related to the project scope
Connect	Establish links with similar or complementary projects
Organise	Systematize information for reuse
Prevent	Integrate mechanisms to prevent duplication
Evaluate	Measure the effectiveness and adjust accordingly

It should also be noted that there are a variety of ways to collaborate with other HE projects, however, some avenues are more resource-intensive (both human resources / staff time as well as financial resources). We suggest that there must be significant synergies in order to engage in high-cost collaboration. The final collaboration list will be a mixture of low-, medium- and high-cost forms of engagement. This is an ongoing process throughout the project.

Low-cost collaboration examples:

- Sharing existing resources (e.g. reports, deliverables) between OH-FINE and collaborators
- Inviting collaborators to online OH-FINE events
- Attending online webinars / events of HE collaborators
- Promoting collaborator events / resources within OH-FINE network

Medium-cost collaboration examples:

- Organising online workshops / seminars
- Developing joint policy briefs
- Inviting speakers to OH-FINE forums
- Developing joint dissemination materials (depending on scope)

High-cost collaboration examples:

- Cross-visits (depending on collaborator resources)
- Joint field demonstrations / field trials
- Organising in-person workshops / seminars

3. Scan of existing projects and networks

To support a proactive and systematic approach to collaboration, a structured long-list of Horizon Europe and relevant legacy H2020 projects was compiled during the Scan phase of the SCOPE methodology. This long-list, presented in Annex Table 1 (and relevant spreadsheet under the “Extended List” tab), documents project focus, AKIS relevance, and potential modes of collaboration. Projects are classified by thematic focus, AKIS relevance, knowledge-exchange mechanisms, potential collaboration formats, and project lifecycle status (ongoing or finished), to support the identification of synergies and prioritisation of collaboration activities. Note this long list goes beyond those projects successfully funded in the 4 thematic call areas within Cluster 6 that are the focus of this report as identified by the commission (specifically HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-20, HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1, and HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-3). This long-list of projects presented was cross-checked against internal OH-FINE coordination and monitoring records, including project-level collaboration and dissemination logs maintained by consortium partners (dedicated shared coordination Excel on the project platform). This review ensured that Horizon Europe projects already engaged through networking, meetings, or joint dissemination activities were captured in the Scan phase (Annex table 2 spreadsheet - “EU Project Communication Tracker” tab). It also highlights future planned areas of communication and collaboration and some other potential opportunities to work with other projects not yet exploited.

Based on the review criteria outlined above, projects were labelled “High, Medium or Low” in terms of priority for follow-up. Projects identified in coordination records that did not meet the Annex inclusion criteria such as non-Horizon initiatives, regional or national pilots, or projects without a clear multi-actor or knowledge exchange focus were not included in the extended list .

The is not exhaustive and serves as a living resource, to be updated as new collaboration opportunities emerge over the course of the project. Moreover, completed relevant projects funded under past calls (H2020) are also identified here as they are a legitimate repository of knowledge, documentation, contacts and network to support capacity development targeted by the OHFINE project. They also highlight the extensive reach of project partners and their linkage to the wider body of related EU research projects in the field

4. Establishing synergies and strategic links (Connect)

Following on from the Scan phase, a shortlist of Horizon Europe projects was established. The shortlist includes projects which show strong potential for collaboration opportunities and fall under HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-20: ‘Developing an EU advisory network on organic agriculture’; HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1-two-stage: ‘Increasing the availability and use of non-contentious inputs in organic farming’; and HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-3: ‘Improving yields in organic cropping systems’. Below, an analysis of each project is provided to pinpoint areas of synergy and mutual benefit. This includes the projects’ relevance to OH-FINE and the potential collaboration opportunities.

4.1 OrganicAdviceNetwork (Grant ID 101134850) (HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-20)

Background

This project builds an EU-wide network of over 1,000 organic advisers across all EU Member States plus additional European countries; emphasises peer-to-peer exchange, online community spaces, in-person events/cross-visits, online learning, advisor capacity building, governance and sustainable funding models for advisory services.

Objectives

- Build a strong Europe-wide network of organic advisers. This includes enhancing exchanges and increasing the visibility and accessibility of organic advice across traditional advisory systems.
- Promote the benefits of organic farming by developing narratives and sharing examples of good practices, as well as explaining core principles like agroecology and regenerative agriculture.
- Enhance advisors’ knowledge about organic practices through activities such as online courses, cross-visits, and multilingual materials.

- Improve advisory methods through diverse advisory approaches, such as group coaching, peer-to-peer exchange, conversion planning, and soft skills training to make advisory work more effective.
- Strengthen organisational capacity of advisory services (including mentoring networks)
- Assess existing policies affecting organic advisory services and formulates recommendations to strengthen policy frameworks in support of organic advisory.

Relevance to the OH-FINE project (High)

- **Direct overlap with AKIS and advisory capacity building:** both are about strengthening organic knowledge flows and advisor/farmer learning systems.
- Natural partner for **joint webinars, cross-visits, and shared “what works” advisory practice notes** (OH-FINE Organic Hubs linked to Organic Advice Network’s advisor network nodes).
- Strong opportunity to **collaborate on dissemination** activities and to communicate OH-FINE outputs into advisor training/CPD formats in the advisor network.

Potential Collaboration opportunities

- Co-host **advisor farmer exchange sessions** (OrganicAdviceNetwork “community spaces” + OH-FINE Organic Farming Learning Community).

Align **resource development:** link the output and communication of OH-FINE’s materials into the OrganicAdviceNetwork channels and vice-versa.

4.2 Organic Yields UP (Grant ID 101137068) (HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-3)

Background

This project address the organic yield gap by

- **compiling & evaluating existing body of knowledge;**
- setting up an EU network of **testing/experimentation/demonstration sites across 11 regions,** and;
- developing **impact strategies and policy/research recommendations;** with a strong emphasis on practical science communication through the showcasing of practice/ demonstration.

Objectives

The main goal is to support organic and agroecological farming systems in improving and stabilising yields — not to replicate conventional outputs, but to strengthen resilience, environmental sustainability and the ability of farmers to make informed decisions.

The project is grounded in two key areas of work:

- Recollecting and adding value to decades of research on organic cropping systems across the EU.
- Mobilising ‘lighthouse farms’ and multi-actor groups to assess, demonstrate, and co-design best practices and strategies in the field.

Relevance to the OH-FINE project (Medium/High)

- Project builds a **multi-region demonstration/testing network** and explicitly focuses on **knowledge compilation and dissemination which would could provide** very relevant content for OH-FINE hubs and network being developed.
- High value for OH-FINE as a **source of practice-ready materials** (yield strategies, regional lessons, demo-site insights).

Potential Collaboration opportunities

- Cross-link demo networks: **OH-FINE hub events** can feature OrganicYieldsUP demo results and methods; OrganicYieldsUP can use OH-FINE channels to reach broader farmer/advisor audiences.
- Potential Joint outputs: **“Organic yield strategies—practice briefs by region/system”** (formatted for advisors + farmers).

Joint workshop stream on **“how to translate yield evidence into advisory recommendations.”**

4.3 SCALE-it (Grant ID 101181496) - HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1 (two-stage)

Background

This project seeks to reduce dependency on environmentally damaging inputs (plant protection products, manure from conventional farms, antibiotics/anthelmintics, synthetic/GMO-derived vitamins) by developing/validating alternatives via a **multi-actor approach, 65+ trials**, local ambassadors, dissemination events, decision/advisory tools, and training packages.

Objectives

The objective of SCALE-it is to increase the availability, accessibility and adoption of cost-effective alternatives to contentious inputs and thus reduce the dependency of organic farming on (a) critical plant protection products, (b) manure from conventional farms, (c) antibiotics and anthelmintics, and (d) synthetic and GMO derived vitamins. As part of the SCALE-it demonstration activities (WP5 ‘demonstration trials’), a series of multi-stakeholder training sessions will be organised.

Relevance to the OH-FINE project (Medium)

- Not a knowledge-network project per se, but it generates a lot of relevant **practice evidence + training materials** that OH-FINE networks could help to dissemination, e.g. through hubs and advisory channels.
- Strong fit for **joint dissemination** and “what works” case content.

Potential Collaboration opportunities

- Investigate potential to convert SCALE-it trial outputs into **OH-FINE learning modules** (short videos, decision sheets, “input substitution” case studies).

Joint advisory-facing webinar series: **inputs, compliance and practical substitutions**.

4.4 BIO2 (Grant ID 101181331)- HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1 (two-stage)

Background

This project seeks to displace the use of environmentally damaging inputs through R&D on novel alternative production inputs, including: fertilisers from **marine by-products + recycled nutrients**, including **biocontrol agents, microalgal fungicides**, and natural antiparasitic treatments. The project involved trials, sustainability assessment and stakeholder engagement to address adoption barriers and investigates industrial scaling options.

Objectives

This project aims to address some of the problems facing organic production in relation to the use of inputs. In particular: the use of copper, sulphur, resistance to pesticides and antibiotics, and pesticide residues present in organic fertilisers. Thus BIO2 try to contribute to replace contentious inputs in organic farming with safe, effective, and circular alternatives.

To this end, it seeks to develop natural solutions in three main areas:

- Microorganisms for crop protection: yeasts, bacteria and microalgal extract
- Bio-based fertilisers: from fish processing side-streams, macroalgae, recycled human urine, and microbes
- Natural animal health products: microbial immunostimulants from inactivated mycobacteria and corynebacteria, as well as bark extracts with antiparasitic properties

Relevance to the OH-FINE project (Medium – Low)

- More technology/R&D heavy, but it will also identify relevant Knowledge Transfer barrier insights, and implementation considerations that can feed OH-FINE knowledge exchange methodologies especially for **innovation pathways** and “from research to practice” translation.

Potential Collaboration opportunities

- Collaboration in **conducting field trials**. Possible inclusion of products developed in BIO2 in OH-FINE field trials conducted on experimental farms and by producers.
- Mutual participation in the workshops organized within the respective projects.
- Joint practice note: **“what to watch for”** (availability, cost, acceptability, regulatory hurdles) based on BIO2 lessons.

- Mutual dissemination of the project content and activities.

Following this analysis, members of the OH-FINE project established initial contact with shortlisted project representatives in a variety of ways (under Task 10.6). Table 2 shows the OH-FINE efforts to establish strategic links with shortlisted projects up until Month 16 (February 2026).

Table 2. Links established between OH-FINE and shortlisted HE projects

Project	Connections made
OrganicAdvice Network	Two meetings held with OH-FINE coordinator (30/01/2025 and 20/02/2025) BIOSELENA) participated in the networking workshop between European projects representing Organic Advise Network Attendance by OFISET at cross visit in Malaga (Spain), organized by Organic Advise Network
Organic Yields Up	First introductory meeting with OH-FINE coordinator (16/07/2025) Attendance by Organic Yields Up representative at Zamora forum (see Deliverable 3.1)
SCALE-it	First introductory meeting with OH-FINE coordinator (22/01/2026) Agreement to cross-post project information on websites
BIO2	First introductory meeting with OH-FINE coordinator (27/01/2026)

5. Follow-up approach (Connect / Organize)

In order to streamline approaches to collaboration as well as connect with other projects listed in Annex table 1, OH-FINE is taking a structure approach to supporting communication and making follow-up actions throughout the remainder of the project:

5.1 Regular update of the OH-FINE coordination tracker

A reporting tracker to track all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities to ensure that the objectives and KPIs of the project are met has been developed and is currently in use (as outlined in Deliverable 10.2). This includes a specific tracker for collaborations and synergies using the longlist of HE projects. The longlist provides a structured basis for initiating contact with a wider range of projects and identifying potential areas for collaboration. Partners seeking to pursue these opportunities should first consult the collaboration tracker to determine whether previous communications have taken place, the nature of any existing engagement, and the relevant contact

persons involved. This review will inform both the appropriate communication approach and the most suitable points of contact.

As a minimum requirement, the coordinating partner must be informed of any proposed collaborative activity. Where other OH-FINE partners are already engaged with the same project, they should also be notified. All collaborative actions must be recorded and updated in the tracker to ensure transparency and coordination across the consortium.

5.2 Follow-up communication and collaboration survey

In order to further streamline collaboration efforts and ensure that there are mutual benefits for all collaborators, a brief survey has been developed to be used with shortlisted Horizon Europe projects. This survey (Annex 2) aim to identify areas where Horizon Europe projects are looking for potential collaboration which aligns with the OH-FINE thematic areas. This survey will be distributed twice per year to Horizon Europe project coordinators (by Teagasc, the Lead Partner for Deliverable 10.3) following initial contact between the OH-FINE project coordinators and HE project coordinators (February 2026 onwards). The survey identifies focus areas for collaboration as well as types of collaboration (e.g. joint field trials, joint dissemination materials, cross-visits). The focus areas and types of collaboration build on the work conducted under WP2. The survey also provides an opportunity for Horizon Europe projects to share upcoming events where OH-FINE representatives can participate.

The survey will be created using Google Forms and responses will be recorded in the OH-FINE coordination tracker. This information can be used by the OH-FINE project coordinators in their communications with other HE projects in order to identify specific areas for collaboration going forward. Together with the OH-FINE coordination tracker this will strengthen the opportunities for collaboration and maximise synergies between OH-FINE and other HE projects.

Annex

Table 2. Long List of Thematically Aligned EU Research Projects

Project acronym	Full project title	Grant Agreement No.	Call ID	Project duration	Coordinating organisation	Primary thematic focus	AKIS relevance	Knowledge exchange mechanisms	Multi-actor approach	Key outputs	Potential collaboration formats
Cluster 6 thematically aligned projects (Task 10.6)											
OrganicAdviceNetwork	Building the Organic Advice Network in Europe	101134850	HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-20	2023–2027	IFOAM	Organic advisory & AKIS	High	Advisor networks, peer learning	Yes	Training, guidelines	High
OrganicYieldsUP	Improving organic yields through knowledge exchange	101137068	HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-3	2023–2027	FIBL	Organic production systems	High/Medium	Demo sites, practice briefs	Yes	Technical guides	Medium
SCALE-it	Scaling up non-contentious inputs in organic farming	101181496	HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1	2024–2028	FIBL	Organic inputs	Medium	Trials, training	Yes	Decision tools	Medium
BIO2	Biological alternatives to contentious inputs	101181331	HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1	2024–2028	ISSMC	Input substitution	Medium	Trials	Yes	Technical solutions	Low
Thematically aligned ongoing Horizon Europe Projects											
HUBRAM	Regional AKIS hubs	101060020	HE	2022–2026	WUR	AKIS hubs	High	Regional hubs	Yes	Toolkits	Medium
FAIRshare	Digital AKIS tools	101000006	HE	2021–2025	WUR	Digital advisory	High	Platforms, training	Yes	Digital tools	Medium
Path2DEA	Pesticide reduction pathways	101060399	HE	2022–2026	INRAE	Low-input transition	Medium	Farmer learning	Yes	Roadmaps	Medium

Deliverable number 10.3 :Collaboration, knowledge exchange and joint initiatives I 6/24

FRAMEwork	Advisory services reform	101061306	HE	2022–2026	JLU	AKIS governance	High	Policy labs	Yes	Policy tools	Low
ClimateSmartAdvisors	Climate advisory services	101060455	HE	2022–2026	FiBL	Climate & advisory	Medium	Advisor training	Yes	Guidelines	Low
FARMWISE	Farmer decision support	101058765	HE	2022–2026	WUR	Farm DSS	Medium	Training, tools	Yes	Decision tools	Medium
yyyyzz\u787h	Digitalisation & data sharing	101000007	HE	2021–2025	WUR	Digital AKIS	High	Co-creation labs	Yes	Platforms	Medium
AgroecologyTransect	Agroecology transition	101061890	HE	2022–2026	INRAE	Agroecology	Medium	Living labs	Yes	Transition pathways	Medium
OrganicTargets	Organic policy & monitoring	101059999	HE	2022–2026	UBA	Organic policy	Medium	Policy dialogue	Yes	Indicators	Low
KnetMinerAgri	Knowledge graph for agriculture	101070123	HE	2022–2026	Earlham Inst.	Knowledge tools	Medium	Digital knowledge	Yes	ICT tools	Medium
ModernAKIS	Modernising Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems	101060888	HE	2022–2026	WUR	AKIS governance & reform	High	Policy labs, stakeholder learning	Yes	Policy tools, briefs	Low–Medium
ATTRACTISS	Innovation support services for agriculture	101060870	HE	2022–2026	ILVO	Innovation brokerage	High	Brokerage networks, training	Yes	Toolkits, guidance	Low
ALL-Ready	Agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures	101000755	HE	2021–2025	INRAE	Agroecology & living labs	Medium–High	Living labs, co-creation	Yes	Practice frameworks	Medium

Deliverable number 10.3 :Collaboration, knowledge exchange and joint initiatives I7/24

AE4EU	Agroecology for Europe	101060907	HE	2022–2026	INRAE	Agroecology knowledge & training	Medium	Knowledge synthesis, training	Yes	Guidelines, learning materials	Low
FARMWELL	Farmer wellbeing and peer learning	101060424	HE	2022–2026	UCD	Social sustainability & peer learning	Medium	Peer learning, case studies	Yes	Training materials	Low
LILAS4SOILS	Living Labs for Soil Health	101060446	HE	2022–2026	WUR	Soil health & co-creation	Medium	Living labs, demonstrations	Yes	Practice guides	Medium
TRANSITIONS	Systemic sustainability transitions in agri-food systems	101060999	HE	2022–2026	JU	Systemic transition pathways	Medium	Stakeholder dialogue, learning labs	Yes	Transition frameworks	Low
Completed Thematically aligned H2020 Projects											
OK-Net EcoFeed	Organic livestock feeding knowledge network	862718	H2020	2019–2023	FiBL	Organic livestock	High	Thematic network	Yes	Practice abstracts	Low
OK-Net Arable	Organic arable thematic network	773911	H2020	2018–2022	Arvalis	Organic arable	High	Knowledge platform	Yes	Guidelines	Low
BEST4SOIL	Soil health thematic network	817696	H2020	2019–2023	FiBL	Soil management	Medium	Knowledge hub	Yes	Factsheets	Low
LIFT	Low-input farming transitions	770747	H2020	2018–2022	Teagasc	Low-input systems	High	Case studies	Yes	Policy briefs	Low
I2Connect	Innovation brokerage & advisors	872687	H2020	2020–2024	ILVO	AKIS & advisory	High	Training, networks	Yes	Toolkits	Low
AGRISPIN	Spreading innovation	652626	H2020	2015–2019	Teagasc	Innovation diffusion	High	Case learning	Yes	Methodologies	Low

Deliverable number 10.3 :Collaboration, knowledge exchange and joint initiatives **I8/24**

SOILCARE	Soil-improving cropping systems	677407	H2020	2016–2021	AUA	Soil & cropping	Medium	Living labs	Yes	Practice guides	Medium
ECOBREED	Organic breeding strategies	771367	H2020	2018–2023	NIBIO	Plant breeding	Medium	Field trials	Yes	Variety recommendations	Medium
LIVESEED	Organic seed & breeding	727230	H2020	2017–2021	FiBL	Organic seeds	Medium	Networks, trials	Yes	Guidelines	Low
SMARTCHAIN	Short food supply chains	773785	H2020	2018–2021	UNIBO	Value chains	Medium	Multi-actor platforms	Yes	Case studies	Low
DIVERSify	Crop diversification	727284	H2020	2017–2022	INRAE	Diversified cropping	Medium	Farmer networks	Yes	Decision tools	Medium
NEFERTITI	Living labs & demo farms	772705	H2020	2018–2022	ACTA	Demonstration farms	High	Cross-visits	Yes	Demo protocols	Medium

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Table 2. OHFINE EU project Communication and Collaboration Record

Cluster 6 thematically aligned projects (Task 10.6)								
Project name	Acronym	Call	Website	OH-FINE partner involved in the project	Type of Synergy/duplicity detected (e.g., data reuse, collaboration, joint field trials visit, workshop...)	Partner(s) who identified	Has been direct contact? (meetings, mails...)	Data contact
Improving yields in organic cropping systems	OrganicYields UP	HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-3	https://www.organicyieldsup.eu/	FIBL-CH	Possible joint workshop/field visits/technical, videos exchange (the project aim to connect actors from science and practice to jointly reflect on organic yield increase strategies).	WULS	By email	Head of the IUNG-PIB team: dr hab. Jarosław Stalenga
Organic Advice network	Organic Advice network	HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-20	https://www.organicadvicenetwork.eu/	Inagro, Bioselena, FIBL-CH		CSIC	Two meetings held; invited to the forum. OFISET talked with María Alonso (ECOVALIA)	ecovalia.projects@ecovalia.org
UpSCALing Efficient alternatives for contentious InpuTs in organic farming	Scale it	HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1	https://scale-it-organic.eu/	BIOSELENA, FIBL CH		CSIC	Coordinator contacted. Meeting held on January 22th 2026	Carla Pinho (Coordinator)

Deliverable number 10.3 :Collaboration, knowledge exchange and joint initiatives **20/24**

NATURAL BIO-MASS AND MICROBIAL BIO-CONTROL AGENT SOLUTIONS	BIO2	HORIZON-CL6-2024-FARM2FORK-02-1	https://www.bio2project.eu	No		CSIC	By mail	alessio.adamiano@issmc.cnr.it
Boosting Innovation in Organic GREENhouses via stronger NETworks	BIOGREENET	HORIZON-CL6-2022-GOVERNANCE-01-10	https://www.biogreenet.eu	FIBL-CH / BIOSELENA	They are focused on organics greenhouse production, so there are not clear synergies or duplicities. Knowledge could be complementary for feeding our platform. Mutual dissemination. Possibility of being interesting for some farmers that want to diversify production	CSIC	By mail	l.schleep@naturland.de
Thematically aligned ongoing Horizon Europe Projects								
Sustainable Parasite Control in Grazing Ruminants	SPARC	HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-19	https://wormsparc.com/about-us/	No	Possible joint field trials/field visits / poster in forum Spain	CSIC	The IGM-CSIC is a partner. meeting with the IP (Maria Martinez Valladares) to explore collaborations and had also invited her to the forum.	mmarva@csic.es
Sustainable Livestock Systems Transition and Evidence Platform for Upgrading	STEP UP - Policies	HORIZON-CL6-2023-FARM2FORK-01-6	https://horizon-stepup.eu/	Teagasc	Potential poster on Spain Forum (Teagasc coordinates, CSIC is involved EEZ)	CSIC	contacted by mail	david.kenny@teagasc.ie / maja@foodscalehub.com /

Deliverable number 10.3 :Collaboration, knowledge exchange and joint initiatives 21/24

								david.yanez@eez.csic.es
Climate Farm Demo	Climate Farm Demo	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CLIMATE-01	https://climatefarmdemo.eu/about/	ILVO, Teagasc , FIBL	Potential Forum involvement	ILVO		Project Coordinator: IDELE (France) Christine Berger, christine.berger@idele.fr
AGrOecOlogy for weeDs	GOOD	HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-02-01	https://www.goodhorizon.eu	NO	Potential Forum involvement		Invited to forum	hfreitas@uc.pt
Evidence-based support for transition to agroecological weed management in diverse farming systems and European regions	CONSERWA	HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-02-01	https://conserwa.eu/	NO			Contacted to invite to the forum (tender portal - portuguese partner contacted)	
Farmer-focused Biodiversity and Agricultural Knowledge Network	FARMBIONET	HORIZON-CL6-2024-GOVERNANCE-01-11	Home - FarmBioNet	Teagasc, Fibl		Teagasc		saorla.kavanagh@teagasc.ie

Deliverable number 10.3 :Collaboration, knowledge exchange and joint initiatives **22/24**

Organic Climate Net	Pilot network of organic farming actors	HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-5 - Pilot network of climate-positive organic farms	https://organicclimatenet.eu/	NO		OFISET	Alvaro Quintana (personally and by mail)	aquintana@ecovalia.org; Stephen Meredith IOA, stephen.meredith@irishoa.ie
Organic Climate Net		HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01	https://organicclimatenet.eu/		Potential poster on Spain Forum (Ecovalia Spanish partner)	OFISET/Betania	contacted by mail	info@organicclimatenet.eu / ecovalia.international@ecovalia.org
IntercropValuES	IntercropValuES	HORIZON-CL6-2022-BIODIV-01	https://intercropvalues.eu/	FiBL-CH	Technical exchange, joint workshop/webinar, dissemination materials,	FiBL-AT		
OrganicTargets4EU	OrganicTargets4EU	HORIZON-CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01-01	https://organictargets4eu.eu/	FiBL-CH	practice abstract, short videos, AKIS	FiBL-AT		
Bbionets	BBioNets	HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-18	https://bbionets.eu	TEAGASC	Digital platform, Interesting documents on collaboration with other projects, multiactor approach	CSIC		Munster Technological University Ms. Carmen Girón Domínguez (carmen.dominguez@mtu.ie) ; Barry.Caslin@teagasc.ie

Deliverable number 10.3 :Collaboration, knowledge exchange and joint initiatives **23/24**

Bioconfarm	Towards a smart plant protection in European farms: An integrated living farm lab approach	HORIZON-CL6-2022-GOVERNANCE-01-12	https://www.bioconfarm.com	NO	Technical exchange, joint workshop/webinar, dissemination materials,	FiBL-AT		andrea.halas@evid.sk
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Annex 2: Collaboration survey for shortlisted Horizon Europe project

1. Under which focus area are you interested in collaborating with OH-FINE?

- Organic Advice, Standards & Compliance
- Crop Management & Diversity
- Livestock Systems & Animal Health
- Mechanisation & Labour Efficiency
- Long term Farm Planning
- Farm processing/adding value to products
- Other: please specify

2. What type of collaboration are you interested in?

- Joint field demonstrations
- Collaborative field trials
- Organise workshop, seminars and meetings together
- Develop joint policy briefs
- Invite as speaker to the forum
- Resources and information sharing
- Develop joint dissemination material
- Participate in training courses - Participate in focus groups
- Visit field trials of other projects
- Other: please specify

3. Do you have any upcoming opportunities for sharing information or networking & promotion in which OH-FINE representatives could participate?

[open answer]

4. Any other comments related to collaboration with the OH-FINE project?

[open answer]